

Terpenoids and Related Compounds: Part VI¹. Chemical Investigations of *Bischofia javanica* Blume

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Bischofia javanica Blume^{2,3} (Fam : Euphorbiaceae) Bengali : Kainjal, is a large evergreen tree which grows usually in sub-Himalayan forests of Bihar, Bengal, Assam and Orissa. Juice of leaves is considered to be cure for sores. *Bischofia javanica* has not so far been investigated. A chemical investigation of the bark of the plant has therefore been taken up. The present investigation of the bark of the plant revealed the presence of epi-friedelanol acetate, friedelin and β -sitosterol as neutral constituents and betulinic acid as the acidic constituent.

The benzene extract of the dried, powdered bark of the plant was separated into acidic and neutral fractions. The neutral fraction was chromatographed on deactivated alumina. The petroleum eluate afforded a solid which on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol afforded crystals, m.p. 289–92°, $[\alpha]_D + 40^\circ$, identical with an authentic specimen of epi-friedelanol acetate (m.m.p.) (Found : C, 81.37; H, 11.25; Calc. for $C_{32}H_{54}O_2$: C, 81.70; H, 11.48%) (Lit.⁴ m.p. 290–94, $[\alpha]_D + 45^\circ$). The above acetate on alkaline hydrolysis and subsequent chromatography of the reaction product followed by crystallisation from methanol gave epi-friedelanol m.p. 277–9°, $[\alpha]_D + 9^\circ$ (Lit.^{5,6} m.p. 278–80°, $[\alpha]_D + 8.7^\circ$, $+9.2^\circ$). The petroleum: benzene (4 : 1) eluate furnished a crystalline solid which after repeated crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol gave friedelin m.p. 256–8°, $[\alpha]_D - 32^\circ$, identical with authentic sample (m.m.p. and I.R.) (Found : C, 84.20; H, 11.71; Calc. for $C_{30}H_{50}O$: C, 84.44; H, 11.81%). The petroleum: benzene (2 : 3) eluate afforded a solid which after crystallisation from methanol gave crystals, m.p. 136–7°, $[\alpha]_D - 36^\circ$, identical with an authentic specimen of β -sitosterol (m.m.p.).

The acidic fraction of the extract was esterified with diazomethane and the crude ester on chromatography over neutral alumina furnished a solid, m.p. 212–7°, which after crystallisation from chloroform-methanol mixture gave crystals of methyl betulate, m.p. 222–4°, $[\alpha]_D + 5^\circ$ (Lit.⁷ m.p. 224–5°, $[\alpha]_D + 5^\circ$), NMR peak at 4.9 ppm (= CH_2) identical

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with an authentic specimen (m.m.p. and I R.) (Found : C, 78.79; H, 10.52; Calc. for $C_{31}H_{50}O_3$: C, 79.10; H, 10.71%). It was further characterised by converting it to acetyl methyl betulinate, m.p. 200–1°, identical with an authentic specimen (Found : C, 77.31; H, 10.38; Calc. for $C_{33}H_{52}O_4$: C, 77.34; H, 10.15%).

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